

Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ phosphor: effect of particle concentration on lighting properties of the 7000K IPW-LEDs

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the white-light-emitting diodes (LEDs) have a vast application on the real-life based on its superior advantages for application in both industrial and civil area. In this paper, we co-doping the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ Phosphor on the phosphor compound of the 7000K In-cup Packaging White LEDs (IPW-LEDs) for improving the lighting properties. By varying the concentration of Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ Phosphor from 0% to 1.8%, the effect of the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ on the D-CCT, CRI, CQS, and LO of the 7000K IPW-LEDs are investigated. Using the Light Tool and software, the research results show that the concentration of the IPW-LEDs has a massive influence on the lighting properties of the 7000K IPW-LEDs. All the results are convinced by Light Tool simulation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the white-light-emitting diodes (LEDs) have a vast application on the real-life based on its superior advantages for application in both industrial and civil area. There are three ways to generate the white light by LEDs for the human eye vision in commonly way as 1) first way is color-mixing from the LEDs to conduct the white light 2) The second is using the phosphor to convert the blue light to the white light in the device called phosphor-converted LEDs, 3) and the third way is the combination of options 1 and 2 to generate the white light [1-6]. In the conventional pc-LEDs, the blue light from the chip die is absorbed by the yellow phosphor to generate the red and yellow lights. The absorption of the red, blue, yellow lights in the phosphor compounding of the LEDs is called self-absorption. The scattering, trapping, and absorption of light are the reason to decrease the efficiency of LED devices caused by energy loss. However, the light scattering and trapping by phosphor particles also increase the probability of light being absorbed by the cup, packaging materials, mainly by LEDs die to improve the optical properties of the LEDs. Here, the lighting performance of the LEDs is influenced by the concentration of phosphor, the thickness of the phosphor-composite layer, the size of phosphor particles, and the curvature of the encapsulating surface [6-15]. From that point of view, improving the lighting properties of the White LEDs (WLEDs) by researching the material in the phosphor layer is need more and more developed and it is the goal of this paper.

In this paper, we co-doping the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ on the phosphor compound of the 7000K In-cup Packaging White LEDs (IPW-LEDs) for improving the lighting properties. By varying the concentration of

Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ from 0% to 1.8%, the effect of the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ Phosphor on the D-CCT, CRI, CQS, and LO of the 7000K IPW-LEDs is investigated. Using the Light Tool and software, the research results show that the concentration of the IPW-LEDs has a massive influence on the lighting properties of the 7000K IPW-LEDs. All the results are convinced by Light Tool simulation. There are some main contributions of this research:

- The IPW-LEDs model is simulated by Light Tools software in the second section with the real LEDs parameters.
- We use the Mat Lab software to investigate the scattering processes in the phosphor layer IPW-LEDs in the third section.
- The effect of the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ Phosphor concentration on the lighting properties in terms of CRI, CQS, D-CCT, and LO is convinced by the LightTool simulation in the third section.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

In this section, the 5600K RP-WLEDs are employed. Figure 1(a) presents a real WLEDs package. Based on this package, the remote phosphor compound is built using Light Tools software, as shown in Figure 1(b). In this model, IPW-LEDs have been configured as in previous studies. The primary parameters of the 7000K IPW-LEDs can be conducted as in [13].

Figure 1. (a) The real white LEDs package, (b) The IPW-LEDs

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The optical properties of Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ particles are configured by using the Mat Lab software based on Mie-theory as in [13, 16-25]. The scattering coefficient $\mu_{scattering}(\lambda)$, anisotropy factor $g(\lambda)$, and reduced scattering coefficient $\delta_{sca}(\lambda)$ can be formulated as

$$\mu_{scattering}(\lambda) = \int N(r)C_{scattering}(\lambda, r)dr, \quad (1)$$

$$g(\lambda) = 2\pi \int_{-1}^1 p(\theta, \lambda, r)f(r) \cos \theta d(\cos \theta)dr, \quad (2)$$

$$\delta_{scattering} = \mu_{scattering}(1 - g). \quad (3)$$

In these equations, the primary coefficients are chosen as in [13, 18-22].

By using the Mat Lab software, the influence of the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ particles concentration on the scattering, reduced scattering and anisotropy coefficients are plotted in Figures 2, 3 and 4, respectively. In this simulation analysis, we vary the concentration of the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ particles from 1% to 5%. As shown in Figure 2, we can state that the scattering coefficients of the wavelength 453, 555, and 680 nm have considerable increase while the concentration of the Ca[Mg₃SiN₄]Ce³⁺ particles rise from 1% to 5%. The scattering coefficient of the wavelength 680 nm is the lowest one and of the 452 nm is the highest one. It can be observed that the scattering of the yellow light in the phosphor layer is higher than of the other one. This

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can be lead to the higher lighting performance of the IPW-LEDs. Furthermore, the anisotropy coefficient versus the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ particle concentration is illustrated in Figure 3 with rising of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ particles concentration from 1% to 5%. From Figure 3, we can see that the anisotropy coefficient of the 453 and 680 nm is the same with each other, but the anisotropy of the 555 nm is higher than others. It can happen because of the anisotropy process in the phosphor layer of the yellow light is better than other ones as the above case of the scattering coefficient. Finally, the reduced scattering process in the phosphor layer of the IPW-LEDs in the connection with the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ particle concentration is showed in Figure 4. As illustrated in Figure 4, the scattering coefficient of all red, blue and yellow lights are the same. From the research results, it can be stated that the influence of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ particles concentration on the scattering processes in the IPW-LEDs phosphor layer is considerable [23-25].

Figure 2. Scattering coefficients

Figure 3. Anisotropy scattering

Figure 4. Reduced scattering coefficients

The influence of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ particle concentration on the CRI is shown in Figure 5 with rising of the concentration from 0% to 1.8%. As shown in Figure 5, the CRI falls from 68 to 61 with raising the concentration of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$. Furthermore, the CQS versus the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ concentration is drawn in Figure 6. As in Figure 5, we set the values of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ concentration from 0% to 1.8%. The CQS decreases from 66 to 62 with the rising of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ concentration. The results from Figure 5 and 6 can be observed that the doping of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}_3^+$ on the phosphor layer has a huge impact on the CRI and CQS of the IPW-LEDs by influence on the scattering processes on the phosphor layer.

Figure 5. CRI

Figure 6. CQS

Finally, the LO and D-CCT versus the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}^{3+}$ concentration are illustrated in Figure 7 and 8, respectively. As shown in Figure 7, the LO has a huge increase from 800 lm to 1400 lm with the rising of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}^{3+}$ concentration from 0% to 1.8%. Furthermore, the D-CCT decreases from 4000K to 1500K while we vary the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}^{3+}$ concentration from 0% to 1.8% as in Figure 8. It can be stated that the higher the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}^{3+}$ concentration, the better LO and D-CCT of the IPW-LEDs. These results agree well with the scattering processes analysis in the above section.

Figure 7. Luminous flux

Figure 8. D-CCT

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we co-doping the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}^{3+}$ on the phosphor compound of the 7000K IPW-LEDs for improving the lighting properties. By varying the concentration of $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}^{3+}$ Phosphor from 0% to 1.8%, the effect of the $\text{Ca}[\text{Mg}_3\text{SiN}_4]\text{Ce}^{3+}$ on the D-CCT, CRI, CQS, and LO of the 7000K IPW-LEDs are investigated. Using the Light Tool and software, the research results show that the concentration of the IPW-LEDs has a massive influence on the lighting properties of the 7000K IPW-LEDs. All the results are convinced by Light Tool simulation and provide a novel recommendation for LEDs manufacturing.

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REFERENCES

- [1] *LED Packaging for Lighting Applications*. "Design of LED Packaging Applications," pp. 215–315, 2011. doi:10.1002/9780470827857.ch6.
- [2] Lin, Yuan-Chang, Jiun Pyng You, Nguyen T. Tran, Yongzhi He, and Frank G. Shi. "Packaging of Phosphor Based High Power White LEDs: Effects of Phosphor Concentration and Packaging Configuration." *Journal of Electronic Packaging*, Vol. 133, No. 1, 2011.

- [3] Tran, Nguyen The, Jiun Pyng You, and F.g. Shi. "Effect of Phosphor Particle Size on Luminous Efficacy of Phosphor-Converted White LED." *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, Vol. 27, No. 22, pp. 5145-150, 2009.
- [4] Luo, Xiaobing, Run Hu, Sheng Liu, and Kai Wang. "Heat and Fluid Flow in High-Power LED Packaging and Applications." *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, Vol. 56, pp. 1–32, 2016.
- [5] Hu, Run, Xiaobing Luo, and Sheng Liu. "Effect of the Amount of Phosphor Silicone Gel on Optical Property of White Light-Emitting Diodes Packaging." *2011 12th International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology and High Density Packaging*, 2011. doi:10.1109/icept.2011.6067015.
- [6] Tran, Nguyen T., and Frank G. Shi. "Studies of Phosphor Concentration and Thickness for Phosphor-Based White Light-Emitting-Diodes." *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, Vol. 26, No. 21, pp. 3556–3559, 2008.
- [7] Shuai, Y., Y. He, N. T. Tran, F. G. Shi, "Angular CCT uniformity of phosphor-converted white LEDs: effects of phosphor materials and packaging structures", *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, Vol. 23, No. 3, pp. 137–139, 2011.
- [8] Sommer, Christian, Franz-Peter Wenzl, Paul Hartmann, Peter Pachler, Marko Schweighart, Stefan Tasch, and Günther Leising. "Tailoring of the Color Conversion Elements in Phosphor-Converted High-Power LEDs by Optical Simulations." *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, Vol. 20, No. 9, pp. 739–741, 2008.
- [9] Li, Shuiming, Kai Wang, Fei Chen, Shuang Zhao, Zhili Zhao, and Sheng Liu. "Angular Color Uniformity Enhancement of Phosphor Converted White LEDs Integrated with Compact Modified Freeform TIR Components." *2012 13th International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology & High Density Packaging*. 2012.
- [10] Liu, Zongyuan, Sheng Liu, Kai Wang, and Xiaobing Luo. "Analysis of Factors Affecting Color Distribution of White LEDs." *2008 International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology & High Density Packaging*. 2008.
- [11] Liu, Zongyuan, Sheng Liu, Kai Wang, and Xiaobing Luo. "Optical Analysis of Color Distribution in White LEDs With Various Packaging Methods." *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, Vol. 20, No. 24, pp. 2027–2029, 2008.
- [12] Liu, Zongyuan, Sheng Liu, Kai Wang, and Xiaobing Luo. 2008. "Effects of Phosphor's Location on LED Packaging Performance." *2008 International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology & High Density Packaging*. doi:10.1109/icept.2008.4606982.
- [13] Tin, Phu Tran, Nguyen Huu Khanh Nhan, and Tran Hoang Quang Minh. "Using Green Emitting Phosphor for Improving Lighting Performance of In-cup Package White LED Lamps." *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)* 8, no. 1 (03, 2017): 125. doi:10.11591/ijpeds.v8.i1.pp125-129.
- [14] Chen, H. C., K. J. Chen, C. W. Hung, C. H. Wang, C. C. Yeh, C. C. Lin, and H. C. Kuo. "Improvement of Lumen Efficiency in White Light-emitting Diodes by Roughened-dispensing Package." *The 4th IEEE International NanoElectronics Conference*, 2011. doi:10.1109/inec.2011.5991804.
- [15] Tin, Phu Tran, Anh Vu Le, Minh Tran, Nguyen Huu Khanh Nhan, and Tran Thanh Trang. "Improving CCT-D and LO of the 6600K ICP-WLEDs by K₂SiF₆:Mn⁴ Phosphor." *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)* 10, no. 2 (2019): 1059. doi:10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.pp1059-1063.
- [16] Michael Quinten, "Beyond Mie's Theory II - The Generalized Mie Theory," *Optical Properties of Nanoparticle Systems*, pp. 317–339, 2011. doi:10.1002/9783527633135.ch10.
- [17] Frisvad, Jeppe Revall, Niels Jørgen Christensen, and Henrik Wann Jensen. "Predicting the Appearance of Materials Using Lorenz–Mie Theory." *The Mie Theory Springer Series in Optical Sciences*, pp. 101–133, 2012. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-28738-14.
- [18] Mackowski, Daniel. "The Extension of Mie Theory to Multiple Spheres." *The Mie Theory Springer Series in Optical Sciences*, pp. 223–256, 2012. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-28738-1_8.
- [19] Wriedt, Thomas. "Mie Theory: A Review." *The Mie Theory Springer Series in Optical Sciences*, pp. 53–71, 2012. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-28738-1_2.
- [20] Mishchenko, Michael I., Larry D. Travis, and Andrew A. Lacis. *Scattering, Absorption, and Emission of Light by Small Particles*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002.
- [21] Zhong, Jiajian, Mingyuan Xie, Zhigui Ou, Rui Zhang, Min Huang, and Fuli Zhao. "Mie Theory Simulation of the Effect on Light Extraction by 2-D Nanostructure Fabrication." *2011 Symposium on Photonics and Optoelectronics (SOPO)*, 2011. doi:10.1109/sopo.2011.5780566.
- [22] Minh, Tran Hoang Quang, Nguyen Huu Khanh Nhan, Nguyen Doan Quoc Anh, and Hsiao-Yi Lee. "Red-Emitting α -SrO:3B2O₃:Sm² Phosphor: an Innovative Application for Increasing Color Quality and Luminous Flux of Remote Phosphor White LEDs." *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, Vol. 40, No. 4, pp. 313–317, 2017. doi:10.1080/02533839.2017.1318720.
- [23] Anh, Nguyen Doan Quoc, Hsiao-Yi Lee, Tran Thanh Phuong, Nguyen Huu Khanh Nhan, Tran Hoang Quang Minh, and Truong Huu Ly. "Y₂O₃:Eu³ Phosphor: a Novel Solution for an Increase in Color Rendering Index of Multi-Chip White LED Packages." *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, Vol. 40, No. 3, pp. 228–234, 2017. doi:10.1080/02533839.2017.1299592.
- [24] Anh, Nguyen Doan Quoc, and Hsiao-Yi Lee. "Improving the Angular Color Uniformity and the Lumen Output for Multi-Chip White LED Lamps by Green Ce_{0.67}Tb_{0.33}MgAl₁₁O₁₉:Ce,Tb Phosphor." *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, Vol. 39, No. 7, pp. 871–875, 2016. doi:10.1080/02533839.2016.1208062.
- [25] Phan, Van-Duc, Duy-Hung Ha, Minh Tran, and Tran Thanh Trang. "Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu₂ Phosphor for Enhancing the Optical Quality of the 6600K CPW-LEDs." *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, Vol. 17, No. 6, pp. 2926, 2019.